

A NOTE ON THE SUPERSATURATION COEFFICIENT AND THE PARTICLE SIZE OF THE SOLUTE

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Wollaston, (*Phil. Trans.*, 1813, 103, 57) observed that finely divided solids not only dissolve more rapidly but also to a greater extent than relatively coarse particles. Gibbs (*Scientific Papers*, 1906, 1, 315), J. J. Thomson ("Applications of Dynamics to Physics and Chemistry," 1888, 25) and Ostwald (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1900, 34, 395) from different theoretical considerations have proposed an equation connecting solubility and the size of particles. Thus

$$\log_e S/S_1 = \frac{2M\sigma}{RTd} \{1/\tau - 1/\tau_1\}$$

where S and S_1 are the solubilities at radii τ and τ_1 ; T , the temperature (abs.); M , the molecular weight; d , the density; σ , the energy per unit area of the surface of separation between the solid and the liquid and R , the gas constant.

In the equation cited above, at any particular temperature and for the same substance, $\frac{2M\sigma}{RTd}$ is a constant (k). If τ is infinitely great, then the solubility S_1 is the normal saturation solubility S_n . Then

$$\log_e S/S_n = k/\tau$$

If $k/\tau < 1$, S/S_n becomes equal to $(1 + k\tau)$ neglecting higher powers of k/τ . The supersaturation coefficient defined by $(S - S_n)/S$ becomes equal to k/τ . The expression $[\tau(S - S_n)]/S_n$ thus becomes constant.

This means that at constant temperature, the supersaturation coefficient of a (supersaturated) solution is inversely proportional to the size of the particle with which that solution is in equilibrium.

This is illustrated by an example from the solubility of gypsum taken from Mellor ("Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic Chemistry" Vol. I, p. 508). Solubility data are expressed in milli moles per litre.

Size	Solubility at		
	0°	20°	35°
0.5 × 10 ⁻³ mm.	14.4	16.5	17.0
1.0	13.5	15.8	16.3
3.0	13.1	15.3	15.75
5.0	12.85	15.0	15.5
From International Crit. Tables	12.92	15.1	15.5

Size	$(S - S_n)/S_n = K$		
0.5 μ	0.057	0.050	0.049
1.0	0.052	0.053	0.052
3.0	0.057	0.060	0.048

Hence 5.0 μ can be taken to be τ_n and the corresponding solubility as S_n .

Considering that the data have been taken from a graphical representation the constants are fairly good.

As a consequence of this law, it is obvious that the introduction of larger size particles would tend to diminish $(S - S_n)/S_n$ or the crystal will grow and converse is the case if a smaller particle than that in equilibrium is introduced. This is in accordance with the experimental findings of Hulett (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 24, 667).